

MODELLING OF THE BALLISTIC IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF POLYETHYLENE-FIBRE- REINFORCED COMPOSITES

Richard Frissen, Leon Govaert and Ton Peijs
Centre for Polymers and Composites
Eindhoven University of Technology
5600 MB Eindhoven, The Netherlands

ABSTRACT

The impact behaviour of polyethylene-fibre-reinforced composites is modelled using finite element analysis. To describe the influence of stacking sequence, the composite plate is subdivided into three layers, each representing a cross-ply of more than 10 plies. The orthotropic stiffness properties are determined using the rule of mixtures and laminate plate theory. Necessary fibre and matrix properties at high strain rates are measured with dynamic mechanical thermal analysis. Numerical results show that especially the out-of-plane mechanical properties have a significant influence on the ballistic performance.

INTRODUCTION

High-performance polyethylene (HP-PE) fibres, produced by solution (gel)-spinning and subsequent drawing, possess unique properties in terms of high strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios. The toughness and the viscoelastic character of HP-PE fibres renders them eminently suitable for applications where impact resistance [1-3] and vibrational damping [4] are required. Due to these unique fibre properties the material is used in ballistic applications such as bulletproof vests, military helmets and protective panels for car doors. These products are constructed of stacked cross-ply lamina or fabrics. These sheets are composed of high-performance polyethylene fibres embedded in a glassy or rubbery matrix. In the case of so-called soft ballistics, the fabrics or lamina are separated by two low-density polyethylene sheets. The low friction coefficient between the adjacent LDPE sheets allows the final product to be flexible (soft). In the case of hard ballistics these intermediate layers are omitted. To obtain a rigid plate, the plies or prepregs are hot-pressed at a temperature of 125°C. The literature describes three different methods to measure the ballistic performance of materials; (i) the V_{50} -test, (ii) the critical velocity and (iii) the weight efficiency method. The first method is a measure for the initial speed of the projectile if 50% of the samples are penetrated at identical conditions. The second is a measure for the maximum longitudinal speed at which a material can be loaded and is calculated from the product of the strain at break and the sonic velocity in the material. The last one is the weight efficiency method and compares different materials by the required weight (often equivalent to thickness), necessary to stop a certain projectile under similar conditions.

Due to the complexity of the impact process of composite materials, the above mentioned methods can give complete different results for identical materials. Many processes, including fibre and matrix breakage, delamination and fibre pull-out, occur during an impact event. In general these failure processes interact and many of them are strongly dependent on material properties, environmental and geometric effects such as temperature [1,3], moisture and shape and speed of the projectile [3]. Consequently, small changes in test conditions can affect the ballistic performance dramatically. At high strain rates the energy storage correlates very strong with the number of broken fibres [3]. Therefore many research has been devoted to the optimization of fibre properties. Impact measurements on HP-PE yarn show that these fibres possess a high elasticity modulus, strain at break and tensile strength. However, due to the influence of the matrix material and fibre/matrix adhesion on the failure process of composites, these optimized fibres do not automatically yield composite materials with optimum impact resistance. Previous studies showed, for example, that improved fibre/matrix adhesion significantly reduces the impact performance of HP-PE/epoxy composites [2]. In the literature, however, hardly any explanation is given about the effects of matrix and interface on the ballistic performance of composite materials.

For this reason fibre, matrix and interface properties are mainly optimized by trial and error, using ballistic experiments. Although such experiments are essential, research on a numerical bases using finite element techniques [5] may provide more fundamental insight because the influence of the different material parameters on the impact behaviour can be shown independently in a parametrical study. The problem, however, of such a numerical optimization scheme is to develop an appropriate model and to find the correct material parameters. Since the moduli of the composite obey the time-temperature equivalency theory and the rule of mixtures [4], both methods are used to calculate the material properties at impact rates. The orthotropic stiffness properties of the HP-PE composite are determined using laminate plate theory. Fibre and matrix properties, which are necessary for the calculation of the mechanical properties (at high strain-rates) of a unidirectional lamina, are measured using Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA). The purpose of this research is to analyze the high-velocity impact behaviour of polyethylene fibre based composites using the finite element program MARC, focusing on the influence of the matrix material and laminate on energy absorption.

THE FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

Non-penetrating ballistic experiments using hand-gun ammunition on a 10 mm thick composite plate have shown that the deflection at the point of impact is approximately 6 mm [6]. Since the bullet velocity decreases, an upper time limit of the duration of an impact event can be found by dividing the deflections by the initial projectile velocity ($\sim 300\text{-}500\text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$). Therefore a time period of $20\ \mu\text{s}$ is chosen in this model, which is long enough to describe the impact response of a composite plates. When a cross-ply HP-PE laminate is hit by a projectile, a longitudinal strain wave will travel through the medium with a velocity of approximately $5\cdot 10^3\text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. After $20\ \mu\text{s}$ the front of the strain wave has travelled 100 mm in a similar manner as a transversal wave pattern which occurs when a stone is thrown in a pool. The material outside a circle with a radius of 100 mm around the point of impact, does not experience an impact. This simple analysis shows that the finite element model necessary to describe the behaviour of a HP-PE composite plate can be limited to a circular mesh with a diameter of 200 mm. Since the material is 'motionless' above a radius of 100 mm, all degrees of freedom at the circular edge of the finite element model can be suppressed.

The composite plate consists of a large number of plies with different fibre orientations. Each layer consists of equally oriented fibres in a rubbery or glassy matrix. Since the dynamic

behaviour of such a heterogenous system is extremely complicated due to reflections and refractions of the wave patterns, in the literature all two- and three-dimensional numerical models describe the composite lamina as a homogeneous system. Three-dimensional models have the advantage of being able to describe out-of-plane stresses and strains in the vicinity of the impact. Two-dimensional models, however, are more cost-effective and easier to interpret. In this research the composite plate is modelled using a thick shell element with a constant shear distribution. The material properties of the plate in the out-of-plane direction are accounted for by the out-of-plane shear moduli and poisson's ratios. The elastically stored energy due to local compression at the point of impact will be small compared to the total energy storage. Especially for relatively thin plates a two- and three-dimensional model will show similar results.

From a computational point of view it is impossible to model all individual layers. The material properties of a symmetric $[0,90]_n$ laminate are calculated using laminate plate theory. It can be shown that the mechanical response of a laminate in bending is hardly affected if the number of $[0,90]$ layers n exceeds the value of ten. Fig. 1 shows the coefficients c_0 and c_{90} , used for the calculation of the bending stiffness matrix \underline{D} from the individual stiffness matrices \underline{S}_0 and \underline{S}_{90} of the two basic plies, as a function of the number of layers n (see Eqn. 1). The values of these coefficients depend on the position of the 0° and 90° plies. The solid line represents c_0 for a laminate with the 0° plies positioned on the outside of a symmetric $[0,90]_n$ laminate, whereas the dashed line represents a stacking sequence with the 90° plies on the outside of the laminate (Fig. 1).

$$[M] = \underline{D} [\chi] \tag{1}$$

$$\underline{D} = \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{d}{2}\right)^3 [c_0 \underline{S}_0 + c_{90} \underline{S}_{90}]$$

where $[M]$ is the column with moments, $[\chi]$ is the column with angular rotations and d is the thickness of the laminate.

Figure 1. The coefficients c_0 and c_{90} as a function of n for a $[0,90]_n$ laminate.

It is clear that these coefficients approach a value of 0.5 if n is larger than 10. The material properties of the cross-ply laminate follow then from the stiffness matrix \underline{S} of Eqn. (2). The material properties of the lamina (\underline{S}_0 and \underline{S}_{90}) are calculated using the rule of mixtures from the fibre and matrix properties.

$$\underline{S} = \frac{1}{2} (\underline{S}_0 + \underline{S}_{90}) \quad (2)$$

In order to take the influence of stacking sequence into account, the modelled composite plate consists of three layers, each representing a cross-ply laminate with more than 10 layers. Each layer is given its own orientation angle using the composite option of the finite element program MARC. The final properties of the composite plate are calculated with this, laminate plate theory based, option. The orientations of the three cross-ply laminates are chosen 0/90 or ± 45 . The composite plate is kept symmetric and the thickness of the middle cross-ply layer is taken 50% of the plate thickness. Table 1 gives an overview of the composite structure.

Table 1. Lay-up of the composite laminate.

Lay-up	outer cross-ply layer 1	middle cross-ply layer 2	outer cross-ply layer 3
number of lamina	2n	4n	2n
orientation	α	β	α
thickness	25%	50%	25%

The composite plate is hit by a rigid bar with a velocity of approximately 500 m.s⁻¹ (Fig. 2a). After impact, only the circular edge of the projectile will make contact with the plate since the plate bends and the projectile is assumed to be rigid. The projectile is modelled by attaching point-masses, represented by the black points in Fig. 2b, to the nodes of the finite element mesh along this circular edge. Consequently, all nodes of the mesh which are hit by the projectile get an initial velocity of 500 m.s⁻¹. The real initial velocity of the projectile before impact is calculated with the law of linear momentum.

Figure 2a. Schematic representation of a plate hit by rigid bar.

Figure 2b. Cross-section of the plate after impact. Black points denote point-masses.

The geometry of the composite plate and projectile are; a plate diameter of 200 mm, a plate thickness of 10 mm, a projectile diameter of 10 mm and a projectile mass of 10 g.

MATERIAL PROPERTIES

At high strain rates, i.e. short loading times, the elastic modulus of the HP-PE fibre is hardly affected by the load frequency [3,4]. Hence, the viscoelastic fibre behaves during the impact process as an elastic material. The material properties of the Dyneema SK66 HP-PE fibre are listed in Table 2. The unknown value for G_{yz} is taken one third of the hypothetical value for a polyethylene crystal since the measured value of G_{xy} is also one third of the perfect crystal value. Since DMTA measurements show a plateau value for the dynamic modulus at frequencies higher than approximately 1 Hz [3,4], the fibre properties as measured at room temperature and normal strain rates are used to calculate the laminate properties.

Table 2. Material parameters for fibre and matrices.

Material parameters	HP-PE fibre (orthotropic)	epoxy (isotropic)	Cariflex 1107S (isotropic)
E_{xx} [GPa]	87	3.4	0.3
E_{yy} [GPa]	3.4	3.4	0.3
G_{xy} [GPa]	1.0	1.24	0.11
G_{yz} [GPa]	0.6	1.24	0.11
ν_{xy} [-]	0.29	0.37	0.33
ρ [kg.m ⁻³]	970	1200	950

To show the difference in impact behaviour for composites with a glassy or rubbery matrix material, properties of an epoxy and Cariflex 1107S based laminate are determined. The material properties of the matrix systems are also listed in Table 2. The modulus of the rubbery matrix, Cariflex 1107S a product from Shell, is measured by DMTA. Fig. 3 shows the mastercurve for the storage modulus and the damping parameter $\tan\delta$ of the material as a function of loading frequency. The value for the modulus of the rubber matrix as listed in Table 2 is taken from Fig. 3 at a frequency of 1 MHz. This frequency is chosen in order to be able to compare the finally calculated material properties of a cross-ply laminate with results obtained from sonic measurements performed at this frequency. Since the duration of an impact event is about 20 μ s, only frequencies higher than 0.01 MHz are relevant. These strain rates are, however, still lower than 10^6 , which indicates that frequencies equal to or lower than 1 MHz dominate the impact behaviour. Note that the frequency of 1 MHz for the determination of the material parameters of Cariflex is within this region.

The material properties in Table 2 are used to calculate the properties of a unidirectional lamina with the rule of mixtures. At high fibre volume fractions ($V_f > 70\%$) the influence of voids in the lamina is taken into account by defining the sum of the fibre and matrix volume fraction smaller than one ($V_f + V_m < 1$). The material properties of a laminate with more than 10 layers are determined from the stiffness matrix \underline{S} (see Eqn. 2), according to the laminate plate theory.

The moduli (E_{xx} , E_{yy} , G_{xy} , G_{yz} , G_{xz}) and poisson's ratios (ν_{xy} , ν_{yz} , ν_{xz}) of a unidirectional epoxy based lamina ($V_f = 55\%$) and a Cariflex based cross-ply laminate ($V_f = 70\%$), as calculated using laminate plate theory, are shown in the third and fifth column of Table 3, respectively. These values compare well with experimental data, supplied by DSM High Performance Fibers BV, shown in the second and fourth column.

Table 3. Experimental data and model predictions using laminate plate theory of HP-PE composites based on epoxy and rubber matrix.

Laminate properties	Tensile tests epoxy UD	Model prediction epoxy UD	Sonic tests rubber cross-ply	Model prediction rubber cross-ply
E_{xx} [GPa]	46.6	46.6	32.8	31.0
E_{yy} [GPa]	3.6	3.62	32.8	31.0
G_{xy} [GPa]	1.1	1.10	0.1	0.30
G_{yz} [GPa]	-	-	0.3	0.28
G_{xz} [GPa]	-	-	0.3	0.28
ν_{xy} [-]	0.32	0.32	- 0.0065	0.0089
ν_{yz} [-]	-	-	0.61	0.53
ν_{xz} [-]	-	-	0.61	0.53
ρ [kg.m ⁻³]	-	1074	952	954.5
V_f [%]	55	55	70	70
V_m [%]	45	45	29	29

The material properties of the epoxy based unidirectional laminate are obtained from tensile and shear tests at room temperature and normal strain rates, since the viscoelastic behaviour of the epoxy resin is negligible. In the case of rubbery (Cariflex) based cross-ply laminates the material properties are measured using ultrasonic experiments at a frequency of 1 MHz. The material properties of an arbitrary unidirectional or cross-ply composite can now be calculated as a function of fibre and matrix properties and both volume fractions.

DMTA

TITLE : F-SCAN
 SUBTITLE: KRATON
 FREQ : 1. 3. 10. 30. 50
 STRAIN : 1
 DIM: 27.90. 5.000. 2.500

Figure 3. Mastercurve of Cariflex 1107S obtained by DMTA.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The impact behaviour of two laminate structures: $[0,90]_{40s}$ and $\{[0,90]_{10},[-45,45]_{20},[0,90]_{10}\}_s$, with an epoxy or Cariflex matrix are analyzed for fibre volume fractions of 55%, 70% and 80%. The ballistic performance is characterised by the velocity decay of the projectile during the impact process. Numerical results show that a glassy (epoxy) matrix gives a better performance than a rubbery (Cariflex) matrix because of the higher out-of-plane shear moduli (Fig. 4). From this can be concluded that the value of the out-of-plane shear modulus of fibre and matrix should be as high as possible. In order to avoid premature failure and consequently a reduction in out-of-plane shear stiffness, a ductile matrix with a high failure strain should be preferred.

If the fibre volume is increased from 55 to 80%, both laminate structures show in the case of a rubber matrix, enhanced ballistic performance. In the case of an epoxy matrix, the energy storage at a fibre volume of 55% is higher than for composites with a fibre volume of 80%, although the latter type of composite possesses a higher Young's modulus. The reason for this is that for epoxy matrix composites, the out-of-plane shear moduli decreases at high fibre volumes due to the presents of voids. This effect does not occur in laminates based on a rubber matrix since the out-of-plane shear modulus of the fibre is higher than that of the rubber matrix (see Table 2). From this it can be concluded that an increase in Young's modulus can be diminished by a reduction of the out-of-plane shear moduli G_{xz} and G_{yz} .

Dependent on the stacking sequence, an orthotropic ($[0,90]_{40s}$) or quasi-isotropic ($\{[0,90]_{10},[-45,45]_{20},[0,90]_{10}\}_s$) laminate is obtained. Based on numerical simulations, the more isotropic composite laminate shows a better ballistic performance. However, the reduced elastic moduli in the principal material directions result in an increase in the stress and strain wave amplitude [7], which accelerates failure and reduces the energy storage in the composite plate. Since the projectile is stopped earlier, local stresses and strains near the projectile will be higher and may initiate failure.

Due to the high longitudinal sonic velocity the high energy density around the point of impact propagates fast through the medium. Fig. 5a shows the deformation pattern, using the first component of the principal strain in the neutral plane, in a $[0,90]_{40s}$ laminate with a rubbery matrix at 100 μ s after an impact by a round bar. Fig. 5b shows the corresponding energy density. It is clear that the longitudinal strain wave propagates faster in the high modulus directions, i.e. the 0° and 90° directions. The effect on the energy density is surprisingly low. The energy density remains high in the vicinity of the impact due to the large out-of-plane shear strains. The energy density pattern propagates mainly with the speed of the transversal wave. The experimentally observed improvements in ballistic performance with increasing in-plane moduli is mainly caused by a reduction of the strainwave amplitude, as a result of a higher longitudinal wave speed. Consequently, failure is postponed and more energy can be stored in the composite plate. This enhanced energy storage does only occur in the fibre directions. Here the influence of the stacking sequence turns out to be a decisive parameter. When the laminate becomes more isotropic, the number of principal material directions with a high modulus increases, whereas the stiffness level in the 0° and 90° directions decreases. When the reduction of the modulus in the 0° and 90° directions controls the impact behaviour, a cross-ply laminate will give the best performance. If not, a more isotropic structure gives a better performance.

The use of different matrices and fibres on the impact performance of composite laminates can be evaluated with the developed finite element model, especially if a failure criterium is incorporated in the model.

Figure 4. The velocity decay of the projectile for a $[0,90]_{40s}$ laminate with an epoxy (dashed line) or Cariflex 1107S (solid line) matrix.

Figure 5a. First component of principal strain for a $[0,90]_{40s}$ laminate and a rubbery matrix, $10 \mu s$ after impact.

Figure 5b. Energy density in neutral layer for a $[0,90]_{40s}$ laminate and a rubbery matrix, $10 \mu s$ after impact.

REFERENCES

1. R. S. Zimmerman and D. F. Adams, Impact performance of various fiber reinforced composites as function of temperature, *Proc 32nd Int Sampe Symp.* 1461-1471 (1987)
2. A. A. J. M. Peijs, R. W. Venderbosch, and P. J. Lemstra, Hybrid composites based on polyethylene and carbon fibres. Part 3: Impact resistant structural composites through damage management, *Composites* 21 (6), 522 (1987)
3. T. Peijs, E. A. M. Smets and L. E. Govaert, Strain rate and temperature effects on energy absorption of polyethylene and carbon fibres, *Advanced Composite Materials* 1 (1), 35 (1994)
4. L. E. Govaert, E. L. J. C. D'Hooghe and A. A. J. M. Peijs, A micromechanical approach to the viscoelasticity of unidirectional hybrid composites, *Composites* 22 (2), 113 (1991)
5. S. W. R. Lee, C. T. Sun, in *Composites Science and Technology* 49, 369-380 (1993)
6. T. Peijs, H. A. Rijdsdijk, J. M. M. de Kok and P. J. Lemstra, The role of interface and fibre anisotropy in controlling the performance of polyethylene-fibre-reinforced-composites, *Composite Science & Technology*, 52 (1), 449 (1994)
7. J. D. Cole, Constant-Strain Waves in Strings, *J. of Applied Mechanics*, 519 December (1953)